

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Laying hen, pullet

Level: Husbandry

Keywords: Behaviour, Enrichment, Housing system, Management

Background context provided by the requestor

Piling behaviour of poultry leading to mortalities is a major welfare problem for pullets and laying hens. Research projects regarding the causes has already been carried out. What is missing are practical solutions to prevent piling behaviour.

Question raised by the requestor

Are there any knowledge for practical solutions that can be implemented in housing of pullets and laying hens to prevent piling?

Answer

This answer to the query n° 2024-007 is largely based on the results of the recent review carried out by Mazocco et al. (2024). Further arguments will be added later in query n° 2024-008 thanks to a survey that will be launched, aiming at gathering practical elements on field.

1. Definition

Piling and **smothering** are abnormal behaviors in commercial laying hens. Piling occurs when hens crowd together in larger densities than would be normally expected, whereas smothering refers to any mortality resulting from a piling event (due to suffocation). Piling can occur relatively frequently and do not always lead to lethal smothering, but smothering is usually preceded by piling (Gray et al., 2020). Piling is recognized as one of the predominant causes of mortality in free-range poultry farming systems (26% of occurrences), followed by cannibalism (6.2% of cases) (Mazocco et al., 2024). Smothering has been reported to account for up to 25% of mortality in organic pullet flocks (Sparks et al., 2008).

When: Piling occurs more frequently during the afternoon. In a Swiss study, most piles occurred between 5 and 10 h after light onset (Winter et al., 2021) and in UK flocks housed in single-tier free-range and mobile systems at 4–8 h after light onset (Winter et al., 2022) when birds are most likely to be using the litter area for dustbathing and other activities.

Where: Piling is often observed in the corners of houses but also against walls, in central areas and in nest boxes (EFSA, 2023).

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Who: In Campbell et al. (2016), duration of piling events ranged from 1 min to 6 h, with 10–230 hens participating. Average pile sizes showed approximately 4–5% of birds participated in piling. Piles were dynamic with birds leaving and joining, and some birds attempting to access the centre of the pile.

In general, it is considered to be three types of piling:

1. **Fear-induced piling (panic):** caused by factors that scare the birds, such as the presence or perceived presence of predators, and is generally the leading cause of high levels of mortality (>20 animals).
2. **Nest-box piling:** occurs when multiple birds seek the same nest box (typically in the corners of the shed, at the beginning or end of the row) for egg-laying. This phenomenon can occur in the early laying phase when the animals have not yet gained confidence in their own nest choice and prefer to follow more experienced ones or during peak laying periods, when there is high demand for nests. This type of piling can result in mortality of small (1 or 2) to large (>20) numbers of birds but are easily identifiable due to their location.
3. **Recurrent piling:** is a phenomenon that, once it occurs, tends to repeat itself multiple times, often associated with piling on top of the litter or in the corners of the aviary, without an apparent cause or reason. This type of piling typically results in mortality of smaller number of birds (1-10) but continues throughout the laying period and the cause remains unknown (Gray et al., 2020).

2. Causes

Whilst nest box and fear-induced piling have apparent triggers, recurring piling does not, making it an enigmatic and ethologically intriguing behaviour. The causes are potentially multifactorial, and this behaviour is thought to be a maladaptive collective behaviour, socially influenced, influenced by early life experiences and caused by hens moving toward or away from an attractant/repellent (Gray et al., 2020).

Main frequencies of piling behaviours are due to solitary birds involved in a wide range of activities (including sitting, standing, and pecking at objects), representing 78% of flocking events, or mass movements of laying hens representing around 8% of flocking events (Mazocco et al., 2024). In Campbell et al. (2016), fewer than 7% of piling events were due to a disturbance. In this and other studies, most piling occurs due to recurrent, apparently calm, 'creeping' behaviour, whereby pullets and hens move towards and underneath others.

Some extrinsic factors that appear to be correlated and directly related to piling behaviour are space availability, environmental enrichment, ambient conditions (temperature, humidity, and lighting), resources like feeders, drinkers, and nests, as well as management practices (Figure 1).

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TRIGGERS OF SMOTHERING IN EGG LAYERS

The relationship between the physical environment and smothering

Figure 1: Relationship between physical environment and piling in birds: causes (Source: Mazocco et al., 2024)

2.1. Fear

Fear and panic can lead to fear-induced piling and, consequently, smothering. Although the slow-moving nature of recurring piling differs from the rapid aggregation of individuals caused by the contagion of fear, components of the recurrent piling behaviour may still be related to fear (Gray et al., 2020).

Fear is defined as an unpleasant emotional affective state induced by the perception of a danger or a potential danger that threaten the integrity of the animal (Boissy, 1995). Genetics, negative experiences encountered from an early stage, and associative learning experiences are elements that have the potential to affect the level of fear in an animal. Fear in birds triggers a complex interaction between their physiology and behaviour, playing a crucial role in adaptation and survival. Laying hens, being gregarious animals, flock together for self-defence and survival. When they encounter a new environmental condition or something that disrupts the normality of their rearing environment, they seek self-defence. Self-defence involves seeking the safety of the group and staying close to better respond to a threat and protect themselves.

Fear can be due to predators, whether aerial or terrestrial (or elements perceived as predators); but also due to aversive practices unrelated to birds' routines, leading to aggregation behaviour in large proportions. The presence of fearful individuals can also induce an increase in fear levels in other hens. This phenomenon implies the presence of social influences in the manifestation of fear, highlighting that the behaviour of one individual can impact the emotional state of others.

2.2. Limited space or access to resources

The movement of birds through space and their interaction with available resources is particularly influenced by circadian rhythms and social behaviours that leads to flock synchrony. Birds naturally synchronize their behaviours and prioritize egg laying in the morning, engage in active behaviours in the afternoon (dust bathing, foraging, wing flapping), and perch at night. The motivation for piling can be caused by the overcrowding at specific locations/resources (such as feeders, drinkers, nests or perches) when the access to these spaces or resources is limited.

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Gregarious nesting, the preference of birds for an occupied nest over an unoccupied one, is a classic example of chicken social behaviour that can lead to piling at specific locations/resources (nest-box piling).

The homogeneous distribution of animals in different areas of the barn is critical. Larger enclosures enable greater dispersion of animals and a higher quantity of exploratory movements by laying hens. This indicates improved welfare and, potentially, a reduced likelihood of piling. Piling is more frequent as group size and population density increase. This is because a larger number of birds can pile up, and birds have social stimuli and preferences more likely to result in abnormal behaviours. Piling with a greater number of animals is also suggested in larger flocks (>12,000 birds compared to flocks of 6000 birds or 6000 to 12,000 birds), regardless of the available space.

The housing system is a factor considered in relation to piling, demonstrating the propensity of the behaviour in slats/litter and aviary systems to be relatively high when compared to systems offering outdoor spaces (free-range areas), which is considered moderate.

2.3. Ambient conditions

The thermo-physical conditions of the production environment (ambiance), encompassing variables such as temperature, relative humidity, lighting, and even solar radiation, can promote piling by making certain areas of the barn more attractive.

Regarding temperature, birds under thermal stress tend to consume less food, drink more water, and increase movement, potentially exacerbating innate behaviours like dust bathing and possibly abnormal behaviours like piling, which can be caused by attraction to warmth or aversion to cold. Temperature variation due to reduced shading in poorly distributed areas, especially on sunny days, as well as opportunities for dust baths and other elements that draw birds to specific locations within the barn, can lead to piling behaviour.

Illuminance and lighting regimes (hours of light, wavelength, and light distribution) affect bird behaviour. Birds have preferences for natural light and certain colours. They will spend more time in their preferred areas in the barn, such as light focal points, nests, and feeders, which can lead to overcrowding and, consequently, piling of animals in certain spaces. Observations of piling initiated by birds' attraction to fragments of external light have been reported. Uneven beams of natural light may enter through openings in curtains or gaps in barn walls, leading birds to cluster either in search of a heat source or out of curiosity.

2.4. Management practices

Good management practices in cage-free farming systems present more challenges compared to battery cage systems. Handlers spend more time dealing with a greater number of variables such as opening/closing gates for paddocks, assisting animals in using unoccupied nests (especially in the first weeks of laying), gathering floor eggs, and dispersing animals when they exhibit variations in even repartition in the barn.

Laying hens are creatures of routine and can be conditioned to behavioural repertoires that benefit the individual or the group as a whole. For instance, it is known that birds consume more food 2 to 3 h before the dark period and before oviposition starts. Improper feeding management, such as inadequate feeding times (especially during laying), changes in feed composition and insufficient food availability throughout the day, can lead to competition among birds, which becomes a stressor that can propel abnormal behaviours, like piling.

Behavioural restriction along with negative experiences generate frustration in the motivation of laying hens. This frustration has a negative impact on the routine management practices carried out within the poultry houses, making the birds more stressed and more susceptible to aversion to human presence and to minor changes in routine. These stresses can lead the birds to engage in small escape flights within the poultry house, resulting in stress and subsequently abnormal behaviours. Because of this, new elements in the routine, such as fans, adverse weather conditions, and disturbances around the barn, among others, contribute to this phenomenon.

Thus, interactions between handlers and animals can significantly affect welfare and, consequently, the behaviour exhibited by the birds, especially during episodes of fear and stress (Mazocco et al., 2024).

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3. Consequences

Some of the consequences of piling behaviour are heat stress, physical injury (such as keel bone damage, scratches and feather damage), and behavioural and physiological stress effects. Production consequences include direct and indirect mortality (smothering and knock-on effects of piling, respectively), potential negative impacts on egg quality (broken eggs and eggs laid out of the nest) and on worker welfare.

4. Practical solutions

Piling and smothering behaviours are usually multifactorial and complex problems that require the combination of several strategies to prevent them successfully. Some of the general recommendations are listed below:

- **Reduce situations that may cause fear.** Avoid sudden noises, rough handling and presence of predators or wild birds.
- **Ensure good and constant environmental conditions** such as temperature, humidity, ammonia and light. Make only subtle and gradual changes. Regarding light, it is necessary to consider that birds may be attracted or repelled to focal points by lights or colours invisible to us, potentially causing piling with no apparent motivation.
- **Provide an efficient and appropriate quantity of resources** such as feeders, drinkers, and nest boxes to avoid competition.
- **Regarding nest-box piling:**
 - Ensure a clear access to nest boxes.
 - Be extra vigilant of the nest during the early laying phase and the peak laying time.
 - Guide the animals to an available and suitable nesting box.
 - Remove birds from overcrowded nest boxes.
- **Provide sufficient environmental enrichment** to decrease the competition and improve the expression of positive and natural behaviours. Various materials can be introduced into the production environment to reduce the possibility of piling occurrence.
- **Provide low stocking densities or large enclosures.** The available area, the size of the lots, and consequently, the occupation density are crucial factors in the establishment and control of piling. Large enclosures and low stocking densities can potentially reduce the likelihood of piling.
- **Choose hybrids** that are less prone to group stress (EFSA, 2023).
- Reduce fearfulness thanks to **dark brooders during rearing** (Riber and Guzman, 2016).
- **Place barriers** to ensure that birds do not become trapped in corners. This may help to reduce mortality during a piling or smothering episode.
- New areas with artificial intelligence are promising. For instance, Morris (2024) developed a smart intervention system based on a camera and an array of light-emitting diodes (LEDs): a neural network is trained to detect piling from overhead images of the aviary floor. Then during normal activities, piling detection is continually performed and when piling is detected, an intervention consisting of a sequence of patterns on the LED array is triggered. Variations on the LED patterns are explored, and the reactions of floor poultry to these interventions are qualitatively and quantitatively assessed during both normal activities and piling. Another example is given with Yang et al. 2024, monitoring activity index of cage-free hens with advanced deep learning technologies.

5. Conclusions

Prevention of piling will require at least some understanding of the biological causes, which might not be easy especially with recurrent piling events. The causes are multifactorial which suggests that different prevention strategies would be

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necessary for successful prevention. To tackle the challenges of piling, will be crucial to evolve poultry genetics alongside field practices and handler care. One goal could be creating strains that are less reactive to different environmental stimuli and stress. This approach aims to reduce negative behaviours and improve quicker adaptation to changing conditions.

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